

FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL TEXTS

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Scientific discoveries and achievements and consequent growth the importance of scientific and technical translation. Every year, with a certain attitude scientific and technological invention, with words new values. Science does not stand still, so the level of translation scientific texts must meet the requirements of the time and technology.

The main feature of the translation of scientific and technical texts is on the one hand, brevity, conciseness, logicity, and on the other hand— complete presentation of the material, without the use of emotionally rich vocabulary used in fiction. The translator of a scientific and technical text must exclude the possibility of arbitrary interpretation. In this regard, we highlight one more meaningful feature scientific and technical texts: the almost complete absence of metonymy, ellipses, antitheses and other stylistic figures

According to Orlova Galina Dmitrievna: "Translation is an art, requiring the ability to concentrate attention so that, while doing particulars, always keep in mind the whole, i.e. the entire text." Professional the translator always performs the translation taking into account the context, because many words have many different meanings, sometimes completely opposite. And for the English language, in particular, such concepts as desemantized and polysemantic words. These events are especially acute appear in specialized texts. For example, the word "jet": in in everyday colloquial lexicon it means "brilliant black", and in aircraft construction - jet aircraft Vocabulary is one of the aspects that must be taken into account when translation of scientific and technical texts. This type of text is different great saturation and concentration of special terms, as well as the presence of lexical constructions and abbreviations, acronyms and initials.

For example: HVAC Systems, HVAC Engineers HVAC is an acronym formed from the words "heating, ventilating, and air conditioning", LPG (liquefied petroleum gas)— liquefied petroleum gas, MC (moisture content)—humidity, HHV (Higher heating value) - higher calorific value, LHV (lower heating value) – low calorific value It is terminological vocabulary that allows you to maintain accuracy,

conciseness in the translation of specialized texts. The term bears the main semantic, informational load, so it should be unambiguous, i.e. it should be assigned only one established meaning. However, since not all terms meet this condition, then translator may have a problem. For example, "oil" - oil, lubricant, oil, "engine" - machine, engine, locomotive. The same term in different sublanguages can express different concepts.

The term "valve" means an electronic lamp, a faucet in heating engineering, valve in engine building, instrument making, hydraulics, "storage" storage device or memory, in other areas actively functions as a warehouse, storage, storage, and accumulation. The technical term "frame" means: a frame in any device, frame in construction, frame in film and television. Therefore, the term functioning in various fields, can be multi-valued another aspect to consider when translating is grammatical features. The compound and complex sentences, infinitives, participial and gerund phrases. In texts of this type, passive, impersonal and indefinitely personal sentences. Therefore, a lot of translation depends on the correct construction of the sentence. Should also take into account the fact that English belongs to analytical languages and Russian to synthetic, which implies a certain word order and different semantic logical stresses.

There are several types of translation of scientific and technical texts:

- Complete (written) translation
- Abstract
- Annotation

Abstract translation – full written translation in advance selected parts of the text, which together form the abstract of the original." How as a rule, the abstract translation is several times shorter than the original text and contains main, key points. Annotation is a concise description of the material. Annotation performs informational, educational function.

Full written translation is the main form of technical translation. As a rule, this type is used when translating instructions, diagrams, and declarations. The meaning of the texts does not change. In modern translation studies, there are many approaches and step-by-step instructions for each of these types of translation of scientific and technical tests.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. <http://buro-perevodov.blogspot.com/>

2. Орлова Г.Д. /Пособие по переводу английской научнотехнической литературы: Учеб.пособие - Тула, Изд-во ТулГУ., 2006 – 175 с.

3. Тимакина О. А.. Курс лекций по дисциплине «Теория перевода» / к.п.н., доц.– Тула: Издательство ТулГУ, 2007. – 165 с.

4. Фомичева, Т.П. HVAC Engineering. Отопление. Вентиляция. Воздушное кондиционирование: учебно-методическое пособие для студентов заочной формы обучения специальности 1–700402 «Теплогазоснабжение, вентиляция и охрана воздушного бассейна» /Т.П. Фомичева, Т.В. Кайко.– Минск: БНТУ, 2013 – 103с.

